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SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERISATION OF CHIRAL MIXED LIGAND CO(II) COMPLEXES: A STUDY OF BIOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE

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ABSTRACT— Chiral Mixed ligand complexes of Cobalt(II), containing two different ligands and one metal center, have been synthesised with the general molecular formula [Co(PCIINAP)(aa)·2H₂O], where PCIINAP represents the sodium salt of p-chloroisnitrosoacetophenone and "aa" denotes an L-amino acid. Chiral mixed ligand complexes have been characterized using various physicochemical techniques, including elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility, electronic absorption spectroscopy, infrared (IR) spectroscopy, and thermogravimetric, differential thermal analysis. Based on the obtained data, the bonding and structural features of the complexes have been thoroughly discussed. Additionally, the mixed-ligand metal complexes were evaluated for their biological significance against selected microbial strains.

KEYWORDS: Cobalt mixed ligand complexes, structural study, biological significance.

INTRODUCTION

Several Cobalt metal chelate containing oxime ligand and amino acid ligand are of current interest for important applications to study biological activity¹⁻¹⁰. The chemistry of cobalt complexes has attracted much attention in recent years because of their applications, in various fields¹¹⁻¹⁴. Researcher interest has shifted from binary metal amino acid complexes to ternary mixed ligand complexes of the type [ML(aa)]¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Among them, isonitrosoketones have been extensively studied¹⁸⁻²⁰ due to their applications in therapeutic chemistry²¹, as well as their utility in various fields of analytical chemistry. Notably, ternary transition metal complexes incorporating amino acids as secondary ligands are significant in mimicking enzyme substrate interactions. In this context, the present research focuses on the synthesis, characterisation, and a study of biological significance of mixed-ligand Co(II) complexes. These complexes involve the sodium salt of p-chloroisnitrosoacetophenone as the primary ligand and various L-amino acids as secondary ligands.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of complexes using chiral amino acids

The Chiral Mixed Ligand CML Co(II) complexes were prepared from respective metal sulphates, sodium salt of p-chloroisnitrosoacetophenone as the principle ligand and various amino acids was used as secondary ligand are L-alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-methionine and L-phenylalanine in 1:1:1 proportion represented by the following equation .

Chiral mixed ligand complexes of cobalt is that they were prepared in aqueous medium. Therefore, present mixed ligand complexes are obtained by green chemistry synthetic route. Thus, apart from being new simple route for synthesizing chiral complexes, the present method could be a new technique for optical resolution of amino acids.

Materials and methods

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. Cobalt(II) sulphate heptahydrate was used as the metal source. The sodium salt of p-chloroisoinitrosoacetophenone was synthesized following the procedures reported in the literature^{22,23}. Amino acids such as L-alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-methionine, and L-phenylalanine were procured from HIMEDIA. Solvents including ethanol, DMF, and DMSO were distilled and purified according to standard methods^{24,25}.

The cobalt metal content in the complexes was determined complexometrically using standard procedure²⁶. Elemental analysis was carried out at the Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility (SAIF), IIT Mumbai. Molar conductance values were measured in DMF solutions of 10^{-3} M concentration using an EQUIP-TRONICS EQ-664ACM-180 digital conductivity meter with a magnetic stirrer (cell constant = 1.0 cm^{-1}). Magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature using a Batra Trading Company Model GMX-TR2 Gouy's balance against $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the standard calibrant. Effective magnetic moments were calculated after applying diamagnetic corrections²⁷. Electronic absorption spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMF using a Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer. Thermal analyses (TG and DTA) of all the metal complexes were performed on a Rigaku Thermo Plus-8120 TG-DTA instrument. Infrared spectra of the ligands and their metal complexes were recorded using an IRAffinity-1S FTIR SPECTROPHOTOMETER SHIMADZU, SERIAL NO. A221354, SHIMADZU CORP. 00525 in the region $4000\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Antimicrobial activities were assessed at Micro Bite Diagnostics, an ISO 9001:2015 certified laboratory (Reg. No. 23EQJJ29).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterisation of metal complexes

All the metal complexes have light brown in colour, insoluble in water, non-hygroscopic in nature and also showed varying solubility in common organic solvents. Their thermal stability indicates having a strong metal-ligand bond between them. Complexes shown -ve rotation value from -69.14 to -232.24 indicated by they are laevo-rotatory optically active compounds, due to the presence of chiral amino acid moiety in the complexes. The elemental analysis data (Table-1) of the metal complexes are consistent with their general formulation is $[\text{Co}(\text{PCIINAP})(\text{aa})_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. The values observed for molar conductance of all the complexes falls in between 0.00033 to $0.00353 \text{ mhos.cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in 10^{-3} M DMF solution, indicate the complexes are having non-electrolytic in nature (Table-1).

Magnetic Susceptibility Measurements

The calculated μ_{eff} values for the Co(II) complexes are obtaining in the range of 5.30-5.45 B.M., (Table-1). which are well within the range expected for octahedral Co(II) complexes. For Magnetic study at room temperature $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ used as calibrant.

Table :1 Analytical data of the Chiral mixed ligand cobalt metal complexes

Complex	Empirical Formula (Formula wt.)	Yield %	Colour	Decomposition Temp. (°C)	%Elemental analysis Found (Calculated)						μ_{eff} (B.M.)	$[\alpha]_{25}^D$ (deg.)	Molar Cond. $\text{mhos.cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
					Co	C	N	H	S	Cl			
[Co(PCIINAP)(Ala)·2H ₂ O]	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₆ CoCl (365.635)	71	Light Brown	242	16.28 (16.11)	36.22 (36.13)	7.59 (7.66)	4.30 (4.13)	-	9.52 (9.69)	5.30	-165.50	0.00105
[Co(PCIINAP)(Vali)·2H ₂ O]	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₆ CoCl (393.689)	73	Light Brown	238	14.83 (14.96)	39.55 (39.66)	7.18 (7.11)	4.74 (4.86)	-	9.09 (9.00)	5.32	-152.12	0.00165
[Co(PCIINAP)(Leu)·2H ₂ O]	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₆ CoCl (407.716)	79	Light Brown	232	14.37 (14.45)	41.12 (41.24)	6.76 (6.87)	5.26 (5.19)	-	8.73 (8.69)	5.35	-216.25	0.00353
[Co(PCIINAP)(Meth)·2H ₂ O]	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₆ CoCl (425.755)	76	Light Brown	250	13.78 (13.84)	36.77 (36.67)	6.49 (6.57)	4.38 (4.49)	7.33 (7.53)	8.27 (8.32)	5.33	-69.14	0.00033
[Co(PCIINAP)(Phenylala)·2H ₂ O]	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₆ CoCl (441.733)	75	Light Brown	245	13.45 (13.34)	46.17 (46.22)	6.30 (6.34)	4.45 (4.33)	-	8.08 (8.02)	5.27	-232.24	0.00056

Where : PCIINAP represents the desalted primary ligand p-chloroisnitrosoacetophenone, whereas Ala., Vali., Leu., Meth. and Phenylala. represent deprotonated secondary ligands alanine, valine, leucine, methionine and phenylalanine respectively.

Infrared Spectral Studies

IR spectra of all metal complexes were recorded in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} to identify vibrational bands associated with functional groups and coordination sites of several carbonyl oxime, several amino acids and their metal complexes²⁸. A band in the 3383–3375 cm^{-1} region is attributed to O–H stretching, indicative of lattice water molecules present in the complexes. N–H asymmetric and symmetric stretching bands of amino acids, typically found at 3286–3170 cm^{-1} and 3086–2947 cm^{-1} , respectively, are shifted to higher frequencies in the complexes. This shift confirms coordination via the nitrogen atom of the amino group. C–N symmetric stretching, usually in the 906–813 cm^{-1} region, shifts to lower frequencies, further supporting N-coordination. The asymmetric COO^- stretch (ν_{asym}) shifts to a higher range (1693–1658 cm^{-1}), while the symmetric COO^- stretch (ν_{sym}) shifts to a lower range (1404–1388 cm^{-1}). These shifts indicate coordination of the carboxylic group via oxygen. According to Nakamoto, Morimoto, and Martell²⁹ the difference ($\nu_{\text{asym}} - \nu_{\text{sym}}$) would increase, reflects the covalent character of the M–O bond. In this study, difference in the range 289–270 cm^{-1} , indicating covalent character in M–O bonding³⁰. For Co(II) complexes, the absence of the –COOH, O–H stretch confirms deprotonation and coordination of the carboxylic group of amino acid moiety. The C=N stretch observed at 1541 cm^{-1} in free PCIINAP shifts to 1470–1465 cm^{-1} in complexes. Indicates coordination via oxime nitrogen. A new band in the 1230–1195 cm^{-1} region is attributed to $\nu(\text{N} \rightarrow \text{O})$, supporting oxime coordination. The C=O stretch of PCIINAP shifts from 1587 cm^{-1} to 1581–1550 cm^{-1} in complexes. Suggests coordination through oxime oxygen. New bands in the regions 705–609 cm^{-1} and 547–451 cm^{-1} are attributed to M–O and M–N vibrations, respectively³¹. These bands are absent in spectra of the uncoordinated Na–PCIINAP and amino acids, confirming complex formation. Some important Infrared spectral bands of all complexes are given in Table-2. Figure-1 is FTIR spectra of representative complexes [Co(PCIINAP)(Phenylala)·2H₂O] as given below.

Table : 2 Important Infrared spectral bands (cm^{-1}) of Co(II) complexes

Complex	$\nu(\text{O-H})$ (H_2O)	$\nu(\text{N-H})$ (asym.) (aa)	$\nu(\text{N-H})$ (sym.) (aa)	$\nu(\text{COO}^-)$ (asym.) (aa)	$\nu(\text{COO}^-)$ (sym.) (aa)	$\nu(\text{C-N})$ (sym.) (aa)	$\nu(\text{C=O})$ (PCIINAP)	$\nu(\text{C=N})$ (PCIINAP)	$\nu(\text{N}\rightarrow\text{O})$ (PCIINAP)	$\nu(\text{M-O})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$
[Co(PCIINAP)(Ala) \cdot 2H ₂ O]	3379 w	3171 w	2978 w	1693 s	1388 s	813 S	1550 s	1469 m	1226 w	686 ^a _w 644 ^b _w	540 ^a _w 451 ^b _w
[Co(PCIINAP)(Vali) \cdot 2H ₂ O]	3380 w	3278 w	3086 w	1693 s	1400 s	902 S	1562 s	1465 m	1222 s	702 ^a _w 636 ^b _w	542 ^a _w 455 ^b _w
[Co(PCIINAP)(Leu) \cdot 2H ₂ O]	3375 w	3279 w	2947 w	1658 s	1400 s	906 S	1581 s	1466 s	1195 s	705 ^a _w 609 ^b _w	543 ^a _w 455 ^b _w
[Co(PCIINAP)(Meth) \cdot 2H ₂ O]	3383 w	3170 w	2978 w	1693 s	1404 s	817 s	1551 s	1465 m	1223 s	705 ^a _w 640 ^b _w	545 ^a _w 459 ^b _w
[Co(PCIINAP)(Phenylala) \cdot 2H ₂ O]	3375 w	3286 w	3005 w	1689 m	1396 s	818 s	1562 s	1470 m	1230 m	702 ^a _w 640 ^b _w	547 ^a _w 459 ^b _w

Where, aa: deprotonated secondary ligands: alanine, valine, leucine, methionine and phenylalanine

respectively, s: strong, m: medium, w: weak; a :PCIINAP; b : amino acid.

Figure: 1 FTIR spectrum of [Co(PCIINAP)(Phenylala) \cdot 2H₂O]

Electronic Spectra

Absorption electronic spectra in the UV region of the metal complexes in DMF solution was recorded. The bands observed in the range 41562-48076 cm^{-1} are assigned to the $\pi\rightarrow\pi^*$ transitions of the aromatic chromophore. In addition, the band observed in the range 29086-29411 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the $n\rightarrow\pi^*$ transition. The bands in the range 27716-28522 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT) transitions. Absorption spectra in the visible of the Co(II) complexes in DMF solution show two transition bands. The bands around 25000 and 18587 cm^{-1} , are attributed to d-d transitions table-3. The ultraviolet and visible spectrum of the representative complex [Co(PCIINAP)(Leu) \cdot 2H₂O] is shown in figure-2 and figure-3 respectively.

Figure :2 Ultraviolet Spectrum of [Co(PCIINAP)(Leu).2H₂O] **Figure :3** Visible Spectrum of [Co(PCIINAP)(Leu).2H₂O]

Table: 3 Absorption spectral data for the CML Co(II) complexes

Complexes	Electronic spectral data in DMF Peak Position $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$ $\{\epsilon \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}\}$		Proposed Assignments
	UV ^a	Visible ^b	
[Co(PCIINAP)(Ala)·2H ₂ O]	48076 (1.411×10 ⁴)		Intra-ligand
	41562 (1.32×10 ⁴)		Intra-ligand
	29103 (1.08×10 ³)		Intra-ligand
	27855 (0.94×10 ³)		Charge transfer
		24968(2.04×10 ²)	d-d transition
		16694(1.27×10 ²)	d-d transition
[Co(PCIINAP)(Vali)·2H ₂ O]	45955 (0.883×10 ⁴)		Intra-ligand
	39556 (1.465×10 ⁴)	-	Intra-ligand
	29411(0.80×10 ³)	-	Intra-ligand
	27716(0.58×10 ³)	-	Charge transfer
	-	24950 (1.77×10 ²)	d-d transition
	-	17035 (1.02×10 ²)	d-d transition
[Co(PCIINAP)(Leu)·2H ₂ O]	46816 (0.976×10 ⁴)	-	Intra-ligand
	41118 (1.066×10 ⁴)	-	Intra-ligand
	29120 (0.82×10 ³)	-	Intra-ligand
	27839 (0.63×10 ³)	-	Charge transfer
	-	25000 (3.15×10 ²)	d-d transition
	-	18587 (1.88×10 ²)	d-d transition
[Co(PCIINAP)(Meth)·2H ₂ O]	48076 (1.492×10 ⁴)	-	Intra-ligand
	41017 (0.541×10 ⁴)	-	Intra-ligand
	29086 (0.72×10 ³)	-	Intra-ligand
	28522 (0.58×10 ³)	-	Charge transfer
		24987 (2.98×10 ²)	d-d transition
		17094 (1.90×10 ²)	d-d transition
[Co(PCIINAP)(Phenylala)·2H ₂ O]	46082 (1.292×10 ⁴)	-	Intra-ligand
	39714 (2.151×10 ⁴)	-	Intra-ligand
	29222 (2.22×10 ³)	-	Intra-ligand
	27855 (1.74×10 ³)	-	Charge transfer
	-	25000 (4.13×10 ²)	d-d transition
	-	18018 (2.17×10 ²)	d-d transition

where a : at 10⁻⁴M concentration, b : at 10⁻³M concentration.

Thermal Measurements

Thermal study TGA and DTA of complexes was recorded in nitrogen atmosphere simultaneously on increasing the temperature from room temperature upto 900°C at the heating rate of 10°C/min. All the complexes investigated shows similar behavior in their thermograms. The thermogram of the representative complex [Co(PCIINAP)(Ala)·2H₂O], is shown in figure- 4 exhibit three steps. In the first step the complex losses two water molecule in the temperature range between 100°C to 210°C indicates that the complex is thermally stable up to nearly 100°C above which it loses the water molecule. The DTA curve of complex displays an endothermic peak at 100°C, which is attributed to the loss of two water molecules. The dehydrated product is stable up to 210°C above that temperature the second step starts. The complex losses some moiety in the temperature range between 210°C to 340°C which could be attributed due to loss of the amino acid ligand. The third step involving the loss of PCIINAP ligand in the temperature range between 340°C to 605°C shown in table- 4. In thermogram the sudden decrease in the slope suggests a simultaneous loss of ligands from the complex which is also reflected by the strong exothermic peak by the DTA curve. There can also be significant contribution to this heat effect from the spontaneous oxidation of the final metal powder formed in the decomposition process into CoO. Thermal study shows the presence of water molecules in the complexes which observation made on the basis of infrared spectral studies and is in good agreement. On the basis of the physico-chemical studies, the proposed bonding and structure in the metal complexes can be represented as shown in figure-5.

Figure:4 TG/DTA Thermogram of Co(PCIINAP)(Ala).2H₂O

Table :4 Thermal Analysis data for Co (II) complexes

Complex	Temperature Range (°C)	% Weight loss		Decomposition product
		Found	Calculated	
[Co(PCIINAP)(Ala).2H ₂ O]	100-210	9.38	9.84	[Co(PCIINAP)(Ala)]
	210-340	24.55	24.09	[Co(PCIINAP)]
	340-605	49.44	49.94	[CoO]
[Co(PCIINAP)(Vali).2H ₂ O]	115-208	8.67	9.14	[Co(PCIINAP)(Vali)]
	208-335	30.00	29.50	[Co(PCIINAP)]
	335-605	46.85	46.38	[CoO]
[Co(PCIINAP)(Leu).2H ₂ O]	105-200	8.33	8.83	[Co(PCIINAP)(Leu)]
	200-325	32.43	31.93	[Co(PCIINAP)]
	325-615	44.33	44.78	[CoO]
[Co(PCIINAP)(Meth).2H ₂ O]	110-215	7.95	8.45	[Co(PCIINAP)(Meth)]
	215-345	35.26	34.81	[Co(PCIINAP)]
	345-609	43.38	42.88	[CoS]
[Co(PCIINAP)(Phenylala).2H ₂ O]	105-195	7.71	8.15	[Co(PCIINAP)(Phenylala)]
	195-330	37.67	37.17	[Co(PCIINAP)]
	330-585	41.77	41.33	[CoO]

Where, R = (CH₃) for Alanine
 R = (CH₃)₂ for Valine
 R = CH₂CH(CH₃)₂ for Leucine
 R = (CH₂)₂SCH₃ for Methionine
 R = CH₂C₆H₅ for Phenylalanine

Figure: 5 Proposed structure of the Mixed Ligand Co(II) complexes

Biological Activities

Biological activities of complexes done by using well method and Antibiotic Sensitive Test (AST).

Well method

Get bacterial cultures of E.coli, staphylococcus spp. and salmonella in log phase by inoculating them in nutrient broth for 24 hrs. at 37°C. This homogenized culture inoculate on nutrient agar slant and incubate for 18 hrs. at 37°C. This fresh bacterial culture is used to make suspension concentration should not exceed than 10⁶ cfu/ml. 1000 ppm concentration solution of all complexes i.e. Ala, Vali, Leu, Meth, Phenenyala, Na-PCIINAP, CoSO₄.7H₂O and Tetracycline was prepared. Then serial dilutions done to get final 100 ppm, 200 ppm, 300 ppm so on till 1000 ppm. After that 3 sets of 2 sterile Mueller hinton

medium containing plates were prepared. Two plates were used for each bacteria. Swabbing of freshly prepared bacterial suspension of E. Coli, Staphylococcus and Salmonella on two plates of each was done and then allowed to dry the plates within aseptic condition. With the help of cock-borer the 5 wells in each plate were made like this complex and blank and positive control sample was inoculated in respective well and labelled them properly. Incubated these plates at 37°C for 24 hrs. The zone of inhibition of all concentrations were measured and observed for minimum concentration at which bacterial growth has been inhibited. As we come to know MIC of all complexes, after that Antibiotic sensitivity test (AST) was checked. It's a comparative study of complex with control tetracycline for antibacterial studies.

AST (Antibiotic Sensitivity Test)

For this method 600ppm concentration solution of all complex, ligand, binder and tetracycline, was prepared. all three bacterial suspensions on three different sterile muller hinton agar plate were inoculated (Swabbing) and inoculation was done of paper disc which was previously dipped and dried separately in all 5 complexes, binder, ligand and tetracycline. Placed plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hrs and results were measured. For Antifungal studies control Fluconazole are used for C.Albicans and control Itraconazole are used for A.niger. In this study MIC found 800 ppm, hence we prepared concentration in ppm of all complexes, ligands and metal in 800 ppm for antifungal studies the result obtained shown in table no.5.

Table: 5 Antibacterial and Antifungal studies of Complexes

Complex	Antibacterial activity at 600 ppm (zone of inhibition in mm)			Antifungal activity at 800 ppm (zone of inhibition in mm)	
	E. coli	Stafalo coccus	Salmonella	C.Albicans	A.niger
[Co(PCIINAP)(Ala).2H ₂ O]	14	10	11	11	12
[Co(PCIINAP)(Vali).2H ₂ O]	15	12	13	12	12
[Co(PCIINAP)(Lue).2H ₂ O]	13	12	12	12	13
[Co(PCIINAP)(Meth).2H ₂ O]	15	14	14	13	15
[Co(PCIINAP)(phenylala).2H ₂ O]	13	11	13	12	14
Na-PCIINAP	7	6	7	7	6
CoSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	8	7	8	7	8
Tetracycline	21	20	20	-	-
Fluconazole	-	-	-	15	-
Itraconazole	-	-	-	-	21

Conclusion

Metal complexes shown higher decomposition temperature suggests that complexes are thermally stable due to presence of stronger bond between metal and ligand. Complexes has shown very low value of conductance hence they are non-electrolytic in nature. From Magnetic susceptibility measurement shown that complexes are paramagnetic in nature with octahedral geometry supported by electronic spectral studies. The FTIR spectral studies show the bonding nature of the metal through N- and O- donor atoms of the two ligands. Thermal analyses of complexes provide evidence for the presence of two coordinated water molecules in the complexes.

The report of antimicrobial activity shown to enhanced on complexation. All the complexes show good antibacterial activity against E.Coli. All the complexes show remarkable antifungal activity against C.albicans and A.niger. Compared to the tetracycline for antibacterial standard and fluconazole, Itraconazole for antifungal standard, the present complexes are less active against the representative strains.

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Conflict of interest

Authors have no any conflict of interest.

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